

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP2 – Outcome Driven Healthcare

D2.7 Workshop for HTA and payer community: demonstrate the OMOP-CDM for generating meaningful HTA + payer evidence (2)

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
AVRU	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL – Switzerland
BI	Boehringer Ingelheim – Germany
HLU	H. Lundbeck AS - Denmark
Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Health technology assessment (HTA) is widely used throughout Europe to make decisions about the reimbursement and/or pricing of healthcare technologies including new medicines. Several countries require evidence on cost effectiveness and budget impact. Important inputs for these analyses are estimates of healthcare use and costs. Companies and HTA agencies face multiple challenges in obtaining and generating such evidence in support of their products. Real-world evidence (RWE) could answer some of the challenges faced by companies and HTA agencies, however progress on the adoption of RWE in HTA is slow compared to the progress made in the regulatory space.

EHDEN work package 2, in collaboration with GetReal Institute, organised a half-day workshop to provide an update on recent developments and discuss progress towards greater use of RWE and the federated data network approach in regulatory decision making by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and consider the implications and opportunities for European HTA agencies and their stakeholders to use the same approach. This involved presentations on the progress of the establishment of the coordination Centre for the Data Analysis and Real World Interrogation Network (DARWIN EU®) by EMA, followed by reflections on this progress and possible implications on the use of EHDEN and the federated data network approach from an HTA perspective. A range of stakeholders also expressed their view on how to further advance the adoption of RWE for HTA. Finally, we discussed how EHDEN and not-for-profit entities emanating from IMI projects such as GetReal Institute can support the adoption of RWE in HTA. A key area of need identified was for the provision of training and upskilling, not only of HTA agencies' staff, but also of committee members, evidence review groups, and researchers. There was also a need for key 'driver projects' to demonstrate the utility of RWE and the federated data network approach in HTA. Assessing the generalisability of trial data is a top priority area for the use of RWE in HTA and, hence, can be a major focus for such driver projects.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) has established the Coordination Centre for the Data Analysis and Real World Interrogation Network (DARWIN EU®). It aims to provide access to valid and trustworthy real-world evidence (RWE) from across Europe on diseases, populations and the use and performance of medicines. This will play a huge role in regulatory decision making, which is often followed by health technology assessment (HTA) to support reimbursement decisions. In the second of 2 EHDEN workshops organised by work package 2 (WP2), we explored the implications of establishing DARWIN EU® and its adoption of the federated data network approach and the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) for HTA agencies and the adoption of RWE in HTA can be further advanced.

NICE, WP2 co-lead, organised a virtual, half-day online workshop on Monday 31st October, in collaboration with Pfizer, WP2 co-lead, and GetReal Institute. The GetReal Institute is an independent, member-led, not-for-profit organisation, with a mission to facilitate the adoption and implementation of RWE in healthcare decision-making in Europe. The workshop was titled ‘*Regulators are formally adopting real world evidence, when will health technology assessment?*’.

The key objectives of this workshop were:

- To provide an update on progress so far in the adoption of RWE and the federated data network approach for decision making by EMA and contrast it with progress made by European HTA agencies and payers
- Understand the barriers to adoption of RWE by HTA agencies and payers
- To facilitate knowledge sharing among all stakeholders and identify areas where IMI EHDEN and GetReal Institute can support this agenda and move it forward.

The overall aim was to develop recommendations to support further adoption of RWE in HTA decision-making across Europe and a roadmap for activities that IMI EHDEN and GetReal Institute can undertake to facilitate this. A list of discussants can be found in the annex. The agenda for the workshop was as follows:

Presentation title	Speakers/Moderator	Affiliation	Time
Welcome and introduction	Dalia Dawoud	NICE/EHDEN	10 min
<i>EMA and DARWIN-EU: Progress and future plans</i>			
EMA: approach to RWE Use	Juan Jose Abellan	European Medicines Agency (EMA)	5 min
The role of DARWIN EU®	Peter Rijnbeek	Erasmus MC	5 min
<i>Reflections from HTA bodies and plans for adoption of RWE</i>			
EUnetHTA21	Niklas Hedberg	EUnetHTA 21	5 min
NICE	Páll Jónsson	NICE	5 min
Moderated panel discussion	Nigel Hughes	Janssen/EHDEN	15 min
Break			5 min
<i>Reflections from stakeholders</i>			
Industry	Hannah Goovaerts	Pfizer/EHDEN	5 min
Patient organisation	Valentina Strammiello	European Patients’ Forum (EPF)	5 min
Academic/clinician	Andrew Morris	Health Data Research UK (HDR UK)	5 min
RWE4Decisions	Karen Facey	RWE4Decisions	5 min
Moderated panel discussion	Shahid Hanif	GetReal Institute	15 min

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Presentation title	Speakers/Moderator	Affiliation	Time
Break			5 min
<i>RWE and HTA: How can EHDEN and GetReal Institute help?</i>			
Capacity building and EHDEN's infrastructure	Nigel Hughes	Janssen/EHDEN	10 min
EHDEN HTA use cases	Ravinder Claire	NICE/EHDEN	10 min
GetReal Institute	Shahid Hanif	GetReal Institute	10 min
Moderated panel discussion	Dalia Dawoud	NICE/EHDEN	15 min
Reflections and Close	Dalia Dawoud	NICE/EHDEN	5 min

2. WORKSHOP

The workshop was opened and moderated by Dalia Dawoud (NICE) and was attended by approximately 100 people from a variety of different stakeholder groups (Annex 1). Dalia Dawoud began by giving a brief overview of EHDEN and National Institute for Health and Care Excellence's (NICE) role within WP2 of EHDEN. The workshop was divided into 3 panels, with the first panel providing an update on EMA adoption of RWE and the OMOP CDM (Juan Jose Abellan) and DARWIN EU® (Peter Rijnbeek). This was followed by reflections from HTA bodies (Niklas Hedberg & Páll Jónsson) on the progress that has been made by European HTA agencies and payers regarding the adoption of RWE in HTA and its barriers. In the second panel, a variety of stakeholders provided reflections about what more can be done to advance the adoption of RWE for HTA. Speakers represented industry (Hannah Goovaerts), patients (Valentina Strammliello), academia and clinical (Andrew Morris), and multi-stakeholder initiatives (Karen Facey). The final panel described how EHDEN (Nigel Hughes) and GetReal Institute (Shahid Hanif) are able to support the advancement of adoption of RWE in HTA, and what more they can do. There was also a presentation on ongoing HTA use cases that NICE are leading within EHDEN WP2, to demonstrate potential applications of RWE to HTA (Ravinder Claire).

2.1 Panel 1: EMA, DARWIN-EU & reflections from HTA bodies

2.1.1 EMA and DARWIN-EU: Progress and future plans

Juan José Abellán (EMA) began by summarising EMA's view on the use of RWE for regulatory decision making by using a quote from the European Medicines Regulatory Network (EMRN) strategy to 2025: "by 2025 the use of real-world evidence will have been enabled and the value will have been established across the spectrum of regulatory use cases" (1). He explained that the Big Data Steering Group set up by EMA and the Heads of Medicines Agencies (HMA) aims to achieve this by setting key actions to be delivered between 2022–25. One of the core recommendations was to promote use of high-quality real-world data (RWD) in support of regulatory decision making, and the establishment of DARWIN EU®. The EMA view is that RWE can support decision making across the medical product lifecycle both pre- and post-authorisation of medicinal products; and HTA bodies and payers can benefit by understanding common ground with regulators and how they can work together.

Next, Peter Rijnbeek (DARWIN EU® Co-ordination Centre) discussed DARWIN EU® and its objectives. He explained that the purpose of DARWIN EU® is to establish and maintain a framework supporting decision making throughout the life cycle of medicinal products and it aims to provide timely valid and reliable evidence from RWD. DARWIN EU® will support regulatory decision-making by:

- establishing and expanding a catalogue of observational data sources for use in medicines regulation;
- providing a source of high-quality, validated real world data on the uses, safety and efficacy of medicines;

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- providing RWD expertise, services and a federated data network including data standardised to a common data model;
- addressing specific questions by carrying out high-quality, non-interventional studies, including developing scientific protocols, interrogating relevant data sources and interpreting and reporting study results.

Although real world data studies have been executed in the past, Peter Rijnbeek advised that the aim of DARWIN EU® is to scale this up to many data sources across Europe. This requires standardisation of health data to a common data model using the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM), and also the standardisation of the analytical pipelines to generate reliable evidence from the data to speed up the number of studies that can be executed within the EU. These analytical pipelines will be created to answer the questions that have been asked by the committees and will grow a list of standardized analytics over time, and onboard an increasing number of databases, and speed up processes to eventually be able to run a large number of studies which matter to the regulator, and ultimately the patient.

In terms of progress, Peter Rijnbeek explained that DARWIN EU® are currently onboarding their first 10 data partners within the data network, with the goal to scale this up to at least 40 within the next 5 years. During the operational phase of DARWIN EU®, they aim to run a large number of studies with different complexities including, incidence rate studies, drug utilization studies, safety studies, comparative effectiveness studies and also studies that can be ran regularly (i.e. every quarter). In the first year they plan to run four studies, but they envision running 150 studies per year by 2025 which would not be possible without improving standardisation.

2.1.2 Reflections from HTA bodies and plans for adoption of RWE

Niklas Hedberg (EUnetHTA21) explained that the mission of EUnetHTA21 is to support collaboration between European HTA organisations that brings added value to healthcare systems at the European, national, and regional level. Niklas introduced the topic by explaining that RWE isn't a formal part of what the commission have contracted EUnetHTA21 to consider. He reflected that whilst there are a few HTA agencies that are beginning to adopt projects on RWE, including Sweden, so far there are few decisions that are influenced by RWE. It was predicted that in the long-term RWE will become more important. It was also noted that whilst the basis for DARWIN EU® is its use for regulatory purposes, HTA would be a very natural expansion of the project. Although there are still several questions about where HTA would fit, there is no better chance to get real world data output than DARWIN EU®.

Páll Jónsson (NICE) then gave his perspective on RWE adoption in HTA. Páll began by demonstrating the potential benefits of utilising RWE, these included helping to speed up access to new treatments and reducing the cost of drug development programs. Pall considered that while people feel that the regulators and HTA bodies have been slow in adopting these types of evidence, the workshop itself suggests that the community is much further down the line towards understanding how broader types of evidence can be introduced into healthcare decision making.

Páll Jónsson advised that there are two key limiting factors that need addressing to progress the adoption of RWE: limited trust in RWE and the availability of good quality data. One element of trust in RWE to consider is that HTA organisations need to be assured that the data are fit for purpose for specific decisions, and this in fact applies to both the regulators and HTA bodies. Work is being done with DARWIN EU® in the regulatory space, but also many HTA agencies are either in the process of publishing or have published their own RWE frameworks. For NICE specifically, the use of data and broader use of evidence is a key factor in the five-year strategy, and this is reflected in the publication of their RWE framework (2). The framework sets out several use cases where RWE is the preferred source of evidence over randomised controlled trials (RCTs), for example characterising patient pathways or populations. There is also a need for understanding what good

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practice is when it comes to all aspects of RWE, and so the framework describes best-practices for planning, conducting and reporting RWE studies to improve the quality and transparency of such evidence. However, there is still work to be done to upskill technical staff and committees to ensure there is enough expertise to judge the quality and the appropriateness of RWE.

In terms of DARWIN EU® and EHDEN, federated data networks allow NICE to scale up the analysis they do and are particularly important in the context of rare diseases where data from an individual jurisdiction isn't applicable, sufficient, or available. However, there are some obstacles when it comes to the transportability of data across jurisdictions, where there can be various systematic characteristics and differences between healthcare systems that influence the patients encounters with them. For example, universal healthcare systems versus insurance systems may have an influence on who seeks treatment and this will be reflected when analysing the different data sources.

2.1.3 Moderated panel discussion

The moderated panel discussion began with a question surrounding the fundamental RWE use challenges between regulators and HTA agencies and whether there is overlap between use cases. The panel agreed that the fundamental difference is that regulator questions are mainly focussed on safety and efficacy whereas HTA questions relate to relative effectiveness and cost effectiveness, therefore they have differences in data requirements. Despite these differences there are potential use cases that could be of benefit for both HTA agencies and regulators, these include use cases focussing on patient population characteristics and natural history of disease. After conducting these use cases, then there is scope to diverge methodologically depending on the focus of the research question.

The next question was regarding the drivers for the choice of data partners for DARWIN and EHDEN. From a DARWIN EU® perspective, Peter Rijnbeek stated that it is necessary to generate evidence that matters to stakeholders, and different stakeholders will have different questions, and these questions are driving the selection of data partners. Nigel Hughes added that one of the key factors is a need for a diverse and representative set of data across Europe to be able to answer all questions that are identified. From a NICE perspective, Páll Jónsson said that NICE would like to see data that reflect the target population, due to regional variation in healthcare and health outcomes. However, federated data networks also provide the opportunity to extend beyond boundaries, especially in the context of rare diseases – where the data from one country alone may not be enough to make decisions.

The final question in this panel discussion was whether there were plans for funding in terms of setting up OMOP CDM infrastructure beyond that provided within IMI EHDEN. There was discussion around work being conducted outside of EHDEN, regarding the setup of national nodes taking the responsibility for the uptake of OMOP on a national level, such as those in Spain and Italy. EHDEN has also set up a not-for-profit entity, which will look for funding opportunities via new Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) projects or participation in other initiatives to push the change management of the OMOP CDM in Europe. DARWIN EU® is also generating a lot of interest and stimulating adoption of the OMOP CDM.

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2.2 Panel 2: Reflections from stakeholders

2.2.1 Reflections from industry

Hannah Goovaerts (Pfizer) began the second panel by providing reflections from an industry perspective. Hannah reflected that RWE offers multiple opportunities to better inform reimbursement by understanding the current standard of care, eligible patient populations, the economic burden of disease and in value-based agreements to assess the outcomes in the real world. Hannah identified some key challenges facing the adoption of RWE. The first was the importance of a consensus on both data standardisation and the increased use of federated data networks. Both will advance national and international RWE projects. The second challenge was to adopt the FAIR data principles and collaborate according to open science principles (3).

There is also the need for future-proof regulation and public-private partnerships to increase trust in data sharing and some structural investments in the health data ecosystem in Europe are to be made for RWE projects to be successful. To advance the adoption of RWE in HTA, Hannah recommended the timely initiation of dialogue in domains where HTA and payer organisations need RWE. This dialogue implicates an anticipation of RWE upstream of clinical and economic evaluations by HTA. Finally, Hannah emphasized the importance of use cases to start learning and establishing experience of the kind of evidence that would be useful for HTA.

2.2.2 Reflections from a patient organisation

Valentina Strammiello (EPF) reflected that patients are very much in favour of RWE generation, and they can contribute to the process of data generation collection. For example, patient organisations active in haemophilia, cystic fibrosis and multiple sclerosis are already working on data generation, and they are developing and managing their own registries. The challenge is to ensure that this is not a unilateral effort and that there are projects that are able to tap into the wealth of knowledge and the information coming from patients. The feeling is that this has not been achieved yet, and that patient organisations are waiting to see whether their contribution will be fully accepted and valued by healthcare decision makers. The key things to consider are the constraints involved, particularly financial and training needs. For patients to be able to contribute, they need to be trained and the organisations need financial capacity to provide this training.

2.2.3 Reflections from HDRUK

Andrew Morris (HDR UK) summarised that HDR UK's mission is to assemble and maintain the integrity of a UK-wide health data research ecosystem. This is achieved by, assembling infrastructure and services which includes standardised analytical pipelines; data standardisation by partnering with EHDEN to drive OMOP governance training; and to create a federated network of trusted research environments to allow data to be hosted and analysed across the UK using the five safes model (Safe people; Safe projects; Safe settings; Safe outputs; Safe data).

In terms of RWE, Andrew shared several learnings. The first is that insights should be taken from the COVID-19 pandemic, where it became necessary to use RWE to establish vaccine efficacy and safety. Secondly, data infrastructure should not be solely funded through classical funding bodies and peer-reviewed grants. Thirdly, real-time data is needed. Going forward it was suggested that EHDEN, in collaboration with regulators and HTA bodies, should identify a small number of high-value 'driver projects' in collaboration with regulators that demonstrate the value of federated data networks at scale. This would provide new evidence and concurrently develop consistent and repeatable data practices.

2.2.4 Reflections from RWE4Decisions

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The final panellist in session 2 was Karen Facey (RWE4Decisions). RWE4Decisions is a multi-stakeholder initiative which brings stakeholders together to discuss what RWD could be collected for highly innovative technologies – when, by whom and how – to generate RWE that informs decisions by healthcare systems (HTA/payers), clinicians and patients.

Karen advised a challenge with RWD is its data quality, and this relates to the earlier topic of trust. Decision makers need to be able to trust where the data comes from and how the analyses has been performed. A range of HTA bodies have produced guidance on development of RWE such as NICE, Haute Autorité de Santé (HAS) in France, and Institut für Qualität und Wirtschaftlichkeit im Gesundheitswesen (IQWiG) in Germany. Furthermore, these developments go beyond Europe, with the US Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) publishing its guidance on use of registries for comparative effectiveness research, and the creation of a National Health Data Strategy in Canada. This is evidence that work is moving forward within HTA, but there is currently a lack of RWD expertise; for example, there is a lack of data scientists in HTA organisations. NICE has invested a large amount in this area, and it is one of the pillars of their strategies; however, not many other HTA or payer bodies have done this, and there is a lack of investment for them to do so. A focus going forward should be the investment in appropriate training for HTA staff.

2.2.5 Moderated panel discussion

The first topic in this moderated panel discussion was regarding training. Karen Facey felt there was a need for upskilling of staff, particularly with a HTA focus. Nigel Hughes spoke about the EHDEN Academy and its HTA learning pathway, which is being developed by NICE and colleagues. The first module has been developed and it aims to provide a basic understanding of why HTA agencies exist, what they seek to achieve, how they approach doing so, and how RWE does inform that process. The next module on this pathway will be ‘R for economic modelling’. There is a recognition that there is a need for upskilling in many disciplines and domains, which presents a large-scale challenge in terms of resources. Peter Rijnbeek added that there needs to be a community approach to building educational material. There needs to be a more strategic way to bring more senior people together who would take responsibility to train others, and this could perhaps be done in collaboration with GetReal Institute. Shahid Hanif said that there have been discussions surrounding academies and organisations that have been interested in generating and developing educational content, and these efforts need to be aligned.

The next part of the discussion focussed on learnings from projects responding to the pandemic and whether this can be extended to other conditions to the same scale without the risk of burnout or using up too much resource. Andrew Morris responded by stating that there should be a focus on a small number of ‘driver projects’, that are both bold and ambitious that would make a noticeable impact to methodology. A goal for attendees of the webinar should be to identify some of these driver projects in the context of HTA. Once these have been executed then the upskilling and training resources can follow.

Karen Facey identified a key challenge within an EU member state context. It is difficult to get member states to align on what their RWD requirements are. HTA bodies should be involved in the national and EU data infrastructure discussions from the outset, to ensure that HTA and payer organisations can access the RWD they need. Juan José Abellán added that the European Health Data Space (EHDS) is a great opportunity to push this agenda. The EHDS is a health-specific ecosystem comprised of rules, common standards and practices, infrastructures and a governance framework that aim to empower individuals through increased digital access to and control of their electronic personal health data. It also aims to provide a consistent, trustworthy, and efficient set-up for the use of health data for research, innovation, policy-making and regulatory activities. This should ideally promote the use of common data models for the benefit of patients, but also for secondary use of the data for regulatory and HTA use.

The final discussion point for the panel was regarding how regulators and HTA agencies can account for real world context when evaluating RWE studies. Peter Rijnbeek began by saying that even though

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standardisation to a CDM helps by standardising analytics, it does not solve underlying heterogeneity in the data. Therefore, it remains important to incorporate data custodians in studies. Not everything needs to be automated and these custodians know their healthcare system better than anyone. Juan José Abellán added that heterogeneity between data sources is something that will need to be contended with but using the CDM will help harmonise not only the data format and content, but also the methodology that is used to make inferences from it. Additionally, the type of data needed for HTA does not necessarily come from routine clinical assessments. Therefore, it needs to be ensured that healthcare systems can gather all the relevant data needed to inform decisions. A workshop discussant added that it is necessary to ask questions of the data that we know we have, rather than asking a question and then finding that there are insufficient data. RWD and RWE is a science and even data traditionally considered as poor can be used, but this must come from asking the correct questions of the data.

2.3 Panel 3: RWE and HTA: How can EHDEN and GetReal Institute help?

2.3.1 Capacity building and EHDEN’s infrastructure

Nigel Hughes gave an overview of EHDEN and a brief update on progress. EHDEN aims to build a large scale European federated data network standardised to the OMOP-CDM. This allows real world health care data to be discovered and analysed rapidly. Analysis is supported by the development of standardised tools and dashboards to visualise results. The EHDEN network is developing and currently consists of 166 data partners with over 650 million patient records. The EHDEN portal can be used to browse Data Partner Catalogue, where one can currently navigate through metadata on 67 EHDEN data partners and to understand which databases are covering which disease or drug areas. The EHDEN academy is a free training resource that can also be accessed via the portal, where users can access 17 courses on skills (e.g. R for patient-level prediction), tools (e.g. ATLAS for designing and executing analyses on observational data) and other valuable learning resources.

EHDEN is now entering its fifth year and is building one of the largest international collaborative research networks. EHDEN has contributed to the understanding of, and response to COVID-19, but also research in wider therapeutic areas. The IMI phase will end in 2024, but EHDEN will continue as a start-up legal entity (created 2021), currently working on sustainability and long-term funding.

2.3.2 EHDEN HTA use cases

Ravinder Claire presented HTA use cases that are underway as part of IMI-EHDEN WP2. The aim was to demonstrate how EHDEN can be used by HTA agencies to quickly produce the evidence needed to address key uncertainties that are barriers to making informed healthcare decisions. One completed use case to demonstrate whether EHDEN’s network of RWD can provide inputs that are commonly required by economic evaluation models was presented. This use case was explored in the context of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (4).

Two further, currently active HTA use cases were presented, one in cancer and one in COVID-19. The cancer use case employs observational data from EHDEN data partners to examine the real-world survival associated with common cancers (e.g., breast, lung) and one rarer cancer (head and neck). Using data from the UK Clinical Practice Research Datalink in the first instance, a user-friendly dashboard provides HTA agencies and researchers with a quick tool to view natural history data for the selected cancers and examine long-term survival projections using different parametric survival functions. The COVID-19 use case includes a multi-database network comparative cohort study, using observational data from the EHDEN network, and explores how such data can be meta-analysed in combination with results from randomised trials. The focus is on identifying the relative effectiveness of treatment for COVID-19 in the hospital setting, namely baricitinib, tocilizumab and remdesivir.

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This work will produce two key outputs. Firstly, an EHDEN Cancer Survival Dashboard that will allow HTA agencies to compare survival estimates received in evidence submissions with real-world survival data and projections. Secondly, novel insights into the comparison between treatments for COVID-19, informed by the meta-analysis of non-randomised data from EHDEN and randomised data.

2.3.3 GetReal Institute

Shahid Hanif presented a background on GetReal Institute and how it can support the adoption of RWE in HTA. The GetReal Institute was established as an independent and sustainable continuation of two IMI projects. IMI GetReal ran between 2013 and 2017 with a focus on bringing together stakeholder groups to develop new tools and resources for incorporating real world data into drug development. Subsequently, the IMI GetReal Initiative ran between 2018 and 2021 to drive the adoption of these tools to improve the quality of RWE generation in regulatory and HTA processes. Both projects emphasised a collaborative approach to producing research outputs, thereby laying the foundation for the GetReal Institute.

The GetReal Institute has 3 focus areas:

- 1 Reducing barriers to the use of secondary data sources
- 2 Bridging the gap between RCTs and RWE
- 3 Addressing evidence needs of downstream healthcare decision makers.

Through these focus areas, Shahid identified several ways the GetReal Institute can support the adoption of RWE in HTA. Firstly, by facilitating coordination of a growing number of global, European, and regional initiatives addressing various aspects of RWD/RWE. Secondly, by providing a sustainable, neutral forum that gives all interested stakeholders an equal voice in collectively addressing challenges in the generation and use of RWE for health care decision-making in Europe. Next, by developing practical resources and tools to facilitate adoption of best practices and recommendations. Finally, by enhancing the level of understanding of scientific and operational considerations for RWD/RWE study designs and methods through research, translational resources, shared learning, research, and education.

2.3.4 Moderated panel discussion

There were two audience polls conducted at the start of this panel discussion. The first asked, ‘Where does HTA experience decision-critical evidence gaps that RWE could help to resolve?’. Results can be found in figure 1. Generalisability of trial data was the most selected option in this poll, however most options got over 20 votes which suggests there are plenty of opportunities to create use cases in these areas. Nigel Hughes also said that this result reinforces the need for very large initiatives to demonstrate the wide-ranging potential benefits of RWD.

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Figure 1 Poll results for 'Where does HTA experience decision-critical evidence gaps RWE could help to resolve?' (PROMS = patient-reported outcome measures)

The second poll asked, 'Where should initiatives like EHDEN and GetReal Institute focus their support for HTA?'. The results can be found in figure 2. Sharing and developing best practices for conducting studies in the HTA domain was the most selected option in this poll, with provision of educational materials coming in second. Nigel Hughes disagreed with the result of the poll from an EHDEN perspective, where he felt that sharing and developing best practices for conducting studies in the HTA domain should be led by HTA agencies, while provision of educational materials does fall within the remit for EHDEN.

Figure 2 Poll results for 'Where should initiatives like EHDEN and GetReal Institute focus their support for HTA?'

Following the polls, the discussion centred around the future and what can further support RWD use in HTA. Nigel Hughes offered two suggestions, the first surrounding data capture. There is a need to ensure that patient outcomes are reflected, and this requires a transition in our model of care in terms of utilisation of such data for clinical care. The more meaningful the data is for clinical care, the better it will be captured and

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then become available for secondary use. EHDS legislation may help clinical data record systems and electronic health records, but they need to improve in terms of the quality of data captured. The second suggestion was regarding training. As demonstrated in the workshop, there is a need for upskilling, and there needs to be a multidisciplinary approach in how it is provided. This shouldn't just fall on the EHDEN Academy, for example, but should begin at undergraduate level and during postgraduate degrees. A discussant also added that not only is there a need to educate ourselves but also a need to educate the people working in the healthcare systems who are responsible for data collection. There should be demonstrable proof that healthcare workers efforts are meaningful and how the data they collect are being used to inform their practice.

The final part of the discussion focused on the future and next steps for EHDEN and GetReal Institute. Shahid Hanif said that there is a need to map out the different stakeholders involved and how they can contribute towards the vision and development of the adoption of RWE. This is a key challenge, to keep stakeholders committed and involved in discussions. These discussions can be used to drive the key projects that are really going to be most impactful for HTA. There is already a culture of performing 'demonstration projects' in the US but there are fewer across Europe. These projects drive learning and help pave the path forward through the act of doing. Nigel Hughes added that more of these driver projects are needed, however action has to be taken quickly because the pace of change is vast. Niklas Hedberg reiterated that driver projects are needed, and that there is a need for stakeholder buy-in, so that these projects can be structured and well organised.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

3.1 Summary of findings

The establishment of the DARWIN EU[®] and its Coordination Centre by EMA aims to provide access to valid and trustworthy RWE from across Europe on diseases, populations and the use and performance of medicines. The ambition is to have at least 40 data partners that have mapped their data to the OMOP CDM within the network and to execute approximately 150 studies a year within the next 5 years. Whilst adoption of RWE in the regulatory space is ramping up, growth within HTA appears to be slower.

There are some HTA agencies that are using RWE in projects, but few decisions are influenced by it. This is because there are still barriers to adopting RWE, such as limited trust in RWE, limited availability of good quality data, and limited understanding of what good practice is when it comes to RWE. There is still work to be done to upskill users to ensure there is enough expertise to judge the quality and the appropriateness of RWE. Several HTA agencies are either in the process of developing or have published RWE frameworks with NICE publishing theirs in June 2022 (2). These can go some way to addressing issues with trust and availability of best practice guidance.

Learning resources such as the EHDEN Academy can help with issues of lack of training, but there needs to be a coordinated, multidisciplinary approach starting at undergraduate level, and broadening training to healthcare providers so that they are aware of why the data they are collecting are important, and how these ultimately impact and improve their practice. Another key theme with which EHDEN and GetReal Institute can support the adoption of RWE and the use of federated data networks for HTA is by defining some key driver projects that would be impactful for HTA. These projects need to be conducted in collaboration with a variety of key stakeholders to ensure that impact is recognised widely and support adoption in HTA practice.

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3.2 Recommendations

- Develop a strategy to create, develop, and promote training resources to help upskill users and beneficiaries of RWE within HTA.
- Identify key ‘driver projects’ that would impact development in methodology and build trust in the use of RWE.
- Start with ‘easy-win’ projects such as focussing on characterising patient populations and natural history of disease, where there is overlap with the regulatory space.

4. REFERENCES

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ANNEXES

List of discussants

Adam	Brooke	NICE
Andrea	Manca	University of York
Ashley	Jaksa	Aetion
Bettina	Ryll	Melanoma Patient Network Europe
Blythe	Adamson	Flatiron
Colm	Carroll	IMI
Daniel	Morales	University of Dundee
Ferran	Sanz	Universitat Pompeu Fabra
Francois	Houyez	EURORDIS & GetRealInstitute Board
Gianmario	Candore	Bayer/WP1 Lead
Ian	Koblbauer	University of Oxford (NDORMS)
Janek	Kapper	Estonian Inflammatory Bowel Disease Society
Jimmy	Toulas	Pfizer
Jon	Campbell	ICER
Julia	Kurps	The Hyve/WP4 Lead
Julien	Delaye	EURORDIS
Manuel	Gomes	UCL
Maria	Kamusheva	Medical University of Sofia
Matteo	Scarabelli	EFPIA
Michael	Schull	ICES
Michael	Van Speybroeck	Janssen/WP4 Lead
Nick	Latimer	SCHARR
Nicole	Yada	ICES
Oresta	Piniakzo	Ukrainian HTA agency
Rafael	Pinedo	University of Oxford (NDORMS)
Sebastiaan	van Sandijk	Odysseus Data Services
Stephen	Duffield	NICE
Thomas	Debray	Utrecht University
Tiago	Taveira-Gomes	University of Porto
Tom	Lawrence	NICE